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Vol. V, Issue 1 (I) September 2015

ISSN 2249 - 7463

IJBMSS

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL
OF BUSINESS, MANAGEMENT AND SOCIAL SCIENCES

IMPACT OF ADVERTISEMENT VIEWING ON CHILDREN'S ROLE AS INFLUENCER IN HOUSEHOLD PURCHASING

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Introduction

Children have obtained larger roles in household decision making so in the purchase decision making process. These small influencers have also formed an entire independent consumer segment in the market. Marketers see kids into three divergent roles, first as a primary market; second, as influencers on their parents' purchase decision; and third, as potential future adult consumers. The present paper focuses on the second role ie the influencer. Advertisers know that the earlier a kid learns about a brand, the more likely she will insist his/her parent to buy the same later (or beg her parents to buy it). This is equally true for the products which are useless or of no use to kids, for instance liquid mosquito repellent, or a toilet cleaner which is of interest to child. Some estimates suggest children see 20 to 30 ads per hour, 55 TV ads per day. There is little doubt that children are affected by television advertising.

Enormous researches have been conducted in the direction, but linking children's advertising and influence tactics has yet to be reported, for the obvious reason that it's difficult to tap children's responses to ads. Children typically have trouble performing research tasks etc. Moreover kids under 7 can't tell the difference between advertising and entertainment.

The present research keeping in mind all the limitations, attempts to find out the relationship between advertisement viewing and child's propensity to influence the purchase decision of the family. The purpose of present study is to examine children's (3-7-year-olds) participation in and general influence on the family decision making process when purchasing household products specially FMCG products.

Hypothesis: At the tender age, a child gets easily carried away by the TV advertisements and family communication plays a greater part in child's expression of interests about different products. It has also been considered that with the growing age, child get more persuasive power and it is natural among female child. Thus the researcher based his/ her study on the following hypothesis

H1: Television advertising viewing is positively related to the Kid's propensity to play a more influential role in: (a) identifying the need of the products under consideration, (b) to participate in the discussion about products, (c) in choice of the product, and (d) actually making parent buy the products.

H2: The frequency of Kid's communication about the product can be associated with his/ her greater influence in the family decision making process about (a) identifying the need of the products under consideration, (b) to participate in the discussion about products, (c) in choice of the product, and (d) actually making parent buy the products.

H3: Age of the kid is positively associated his/ her propensity to play a more influential role in (a) identifying the need of the products under consideration, (b) to participate in the discussion about products, (c) in choice of the product, and (d) actually making parent buy the products.

H4: Female kids are more likely than their male counterparts to have influence over her parents in (a) identifying the need of the products under consideration, (b) to participate in the discussion about products, (c) in choice of the product, and (d) actually making parent buy the products.

Methodology

Sample

Kids from Delhi and greater Noida area from primary schools were interviewed (unstructured). 7 schools, demographically representative of their respective regions were selected after permission with school officials to ascertain the responses

Kids were also given a questionnaire to take home to be filled by their parents. The questionnaire was designed for the child's mother. The questionnaire contained questions to find out the demographic characteristics of the child who brought the questionnaire to her, so as to match the parent's anonymous questionnaire responses to the respective child's response.

The study considers the responses given by both child and the parent, which makes the research unique in itself. As most previous researches in this area used responses from either parties. Specifically, measures of the independent variables (e.g., television viewing, family communication about consumption) were obtained from kids, whereas measures of dependent variables were solicited from the child's mother. The rationale for using this method, instead of surveying only parents or children, was based on the assumption that the kid is in a better position to provide accurate information on his/her interaction with TV, whereas the mother is in a better position to assess the child's influence on the Outcome of various types of consumer decisions.

A total of 37 parent-child pairs were obtained from the effort. Gathering responses from kids was a tactful task thus Kids and parents were also interviewed randomly at malls during peak hours of Sunday so as to get more accurate and prompt response. Through the entire exercise total of 56 responses were gathered for the study.

The non respondents were those who were reluctant to participate in the study and parents who did not respond to questionnaires for several reasons, but the specification of non response rates in these groups was not possible.

Definition and Measurement of Variables

Definition of Kid: For the purpose of research a kid is defined as a normal person in the age limit of 3 to 7 years of age having exposure to television advertisements.

Dependent and Independent variables: Independent variables are Age, sex and frequency of TV advertisement views and dependent variables consists of kid's communication with the family regarding (a) identifying the need of the products under consideration, (b) to participate in the discussion about products, (c) in choice of the product, and (d) actually making parent buy the products.

There are various roles a kid can play in the purchase decision making of parent, he/she can act an initiator, influencer, decider, gatekeeper. This conceptualization shaped respective measures to consider. Specifically, relative parent-child measures were obtained by asking mothers to tell about the one who generally mention the need or discuss buying or insist purchase of the product. The products under study were not specific to one segment in particular but any product which has an influential TV advertise was the subject of study. It is being kept in mind that any product even though it is of no use to a kid still influence his/her thinking process (Catchy taglines, colorful appearance or even the character shown in the ads) and represent various levels of relevance to the child's vis-a-vis family's consumption or use, providing several opportunities for parent and child involvement; in addition, moreover only FMCG products were taken into consideration keeping in mind the ease and convenience of shopping. The response alternatives were parent or child or both parent and child. Thus, the dependent variables are (a) identification of the products need (b) participation in the discussion about products, (c) choice of the product, and (d) actually making parent buy the product.

The kid as purchase initiator refers to the child's relative possibility of identifying the need for a product. It was measured by summing responses to those products the mother indicated the child usually mentions the need for. The alpha reliability coefficient of this 0 to 8 point scale was 0.68.

The kid as influencer refers to the kid's relative propensity to "discuss buying" with family members about the product. It was measured by summing responses to those products the mother indicated the child generally discusses buying. The alpha coefficient of this 0 to 8 point scale was .68.

The kid as decider refers to the kid's relative propensity to decide what to buy. It was measured by summing responses to those products the mother indicated the child usually decides what to buy. The reliability coefficient of this 0 to 8 point scale was .59.

The kid's role as purchaser refers to the adolescent's relative propensity to buy products. It was measured by summing responses to those products the mother indicated the child actually make the parent buy. The reliability coefficient of this 0 to 8 point scale was .67.

For the present research kid's Communication about consumption was defined as obvious kid's interaction concerning products. It was measured by summing responses to eight items such as "My child talks about buying things (as was asked to parents)," on a five-point "very often" (5) to "never" (1) scale; the alpha reliability coefficient of this 0 to 8 point scale was .76.

Table 1
Means (X), Standard deviation (SD), Range and correlation matrix for dependend and independent variables

Variables	X	SD	Range	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
8	9	10								
kid identifies the product need		2.7	1.6	0-6	1.0					
kid participate in the discussion about products			0.9	1.3	0-6	0.54	.10			
kid participate in choice of the product			1.0	1.4	0-4	0.53	.56	1.0		
kid make parent buy the products			.8	.13	0-6	.34	.39	.67	1.0	
Television Viewing		15	4.3	3- 8	-.10	-.05	-.15	-.05	1.0	
Age	1.5	.5	1-3	.18	-.06	.01	-.21	.07	0.6	
Sex	8.1	1.8	3-7	.33	.32	.33	.35	-.34	-.32	.34

Note: Correlations of approximately 0.14 or greater are significant at beyond .05 level.

Table 2
Relationship between measures of child participation in consumer decision and independent variables

Dependent Variables	kid identifies the product need	kid participate in the discussion about products	kid participate in choice of the product	kid is actually buying products.
Independent variables				
Age	.20	.15	.31	.27
Sex	.20	.25	.27	.15
TV viewing	.14	.26	.23	.16
Kid's communication	.17	.21	.22	.35

about the product

Note: Table entries are partial correlation coefficients

1. *p .05
2. ** p .01
3. *** p .001

Results

The relationship among dependent and independent variables are shown in Table No.1. The results indicate a positive association of television advertising viewing and family communications. Although age of a child is negatively related with the family communication as contrast to prevailing believes.

Partial correlations between measures of kid's participation in consumer decisions and the independent variables are shown in table 2.

The results indicate a positive relationship between age with all four dependent measures, as positive. Particularly, the older the child is, the more are the chances of his/ her role in mentioning the need for products (r-.20, p<.01), kids participation in discussion about product (r-.15, p<.05), making choice of the product (r-.31, p<.001), and actually making parent buy the products (r-.27, p<.01). The given data validates hypothesis 3.

The data also supports hypothesis 4 which talks about the effects of gender (sex) on(a) identifying the need of the products under consideration, (b) to participate in the discussion about products, (c) in choice of the product, and (d) actually makes parent buy the products. The data validate the fact that, female kids are more likely than their male counterparts to identifying the need of the products under consideration (r-.20, p<.05), participate in the discussion about products (r-.25, p<.001), making choice of the product (r-.27, p<.001), and actually makes parent buy the products (r-.15, p<.05)

The results strongly establishes that television viewing is positively associated with identification of the need of the products under consideration by the child (r-.14, p<.05), participation in the discussion about products

($r = -0.26$, $p < 0.001$), making choice of the product ($r = -0.23$, $p < 0.001$), and actually making parent buy the products ($r = 0.16$, $p < 0.05$)

As expected, advertisement viewing frequency is associated with all the four measures of the kid's participation in consumer decisions, providing good support to Hypothesis 1.

Kid's communication about product was positively related to most dependent measures. Specifically, the more frequently the kid communicate about the product, the more likely s/he is to play a major role in identifying the need of the products under consideration ($r = -0.17$, $p < 0.05$), participate in the discussion about products ($r = -0.21$, $p < 0.001$), making choice of the product ($r = -0.22$, $p < 0.001$), and actually makes parent buy the products ($r = -0.35$, $p < 0.001$) Thus the data validates Hypothesis 2.

Discussion

The research conducted confirms the relationship between the frequency of viewing a particular product's advertisement and measures of kid's participation in the purchase decision of that product. The point to consider here is that, the present study was conducted for the adult or family products which are of no use to kids, still the kid insist such purchase. Thus, consequences of television advertising effects as presented by Adler (1977) on young children's purchase behavior is not the right parameter to compare as the said study was about children's product not about adult's product.

Television advertising viewing was not associated with any dependent measure of the child's relative participation and influence in consumer decisions. Although previous studies have shown television advertising effects on the youth's cognitions, attitudes, and behaviors, the results of the present study suggest that TV advertising viewing has impact on household consumer decisions. As established by the present study child acts as a "selling agent" for the seller of advertised products, the given data have shown significant relationships between the frequency of viewing of such ads and measures of the kid's relative participation in family decision making regarding purchase.

There are number of reasons which can be held responsible for the inconsistency in the present results with those of previous studies. Firstly, researches in this direction are mainly focused on television advertising effects mostly with adolescents, as children (specially very young) are not are not considered an and influencing factor in household buying specially for the products which are not of any interest to them. Secondly, previous researches evaluated advertising consequences in the context of the child's consumption behavior rather than household decision making. Thirdly in previous studies self reported influences or parent's responses are studies rather than co relational evidences, and these are basically focused on few product categories. Fourthly measures of advertising exposure have normally used, amount of time spent viewing TV, rather than time and motivations for viewing TV ads. Finally in the previous studies, measures of the child's were absolute to the extent to which the child insisted the purchase advertised product; the measures in present research were relative i.e., the child's influence in parental purchase which includes parent as well as child's influence.

A child's involvement in purchase decisions appears to be a function of advertisement viewing on television and the characters shown in the advertisement. The child sees his/her personality in the child character in advertisement and thus keeping himself/herself in the place of character insist buying of such products in which he or she has no interest as such.

The point worth noticing is that with the increasing age, kids shows greater participation in consumer decisions (although kids aged between 3 to 7 were considered). This may be due with the age they generate more knowledge about the marketplace and start understanding the use of paper currency, moreover it is interesting to learn that female kids showed more likelihood of being involved in consumer decision making as compared to their male counterparts possibly due their natural inclination towards shopping or due to parental encouragement.

The frequency of kid's interaction with TV advertises was a fairly good predictor of involvement in the early stages of consumer decisions and the present study validates the impact of TV advertisement on kids role as an influencer in the family purchase decision.

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